

THE DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF SCALE FOR THE THREE LEVELS OF INTERCULTURAL AWARENESS

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Abstract

Background: The enhancement of global cooperation led to a significant focus on intercultural awareness within the field of English teaching in China. However, there is a lack of research on the evaluation of the three levels of intercultural awareness according to Baker's (2012) theory. Method: This study has undertaken a literature assessment concerning scales of intercultural awareness in order to provide a framework for constructing a scale including three levels of intercultural awareness. The construction of the intercultural awareness scale was first based on a thorough examination of existing material. Subsequently, adjustments have been made to the questionnaire based on the validation conducted by the expert group. Following the adjustment, a total of 274 students from a higher vocational college in Henan province, China, have completed the scale. The final draft of the scale has been amended based on the findings obtained from the SPSS analysis. Results: According to the findings of the SPSS analysis, the scale measuring the three levels of intercultural awareness demonstrates both validity and reliability. Additionally, the findings of the component analysis suggest that the three levels of intercultural awareness in the scale presented are reasonable. Furthermore, the evaluation findings of the structural model indicate that the three-level intercultural awareness model is deemed adequate. Conclusion: The present study aims to develop an intercultural awareness scale for students learning English as a foreign language (EFL), drawing upon the theoretical framework proposed by Will Baker. This research instrument will serve as a valuable tool for assessing students' intercultural awareness levels, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of English language education.

Keywords: Intercultural Awareness, Scale Development, EFL

1. INTRODUCTION

Language is a component of culture. Hence, the instruction of English as a second language is essential in relation to the cultural aspects prevalent in English-speaking nations. English holds significant importance as a fundamental public subject within China's higher vocational education system. The finalization of the Higher-vocational English Curriculum Standard (2021) occurred in March 2021. This standard comprises four components, namely: language as a method of communication, language as a vehicle for cultural transmission, language as a cognitive tool, and the subjective experiences of learners. The second portion of concentration within the higher-vocational English curriculum is the awareness and understanding of cultural diversity (Wen Qiufang & Zhang Hong, 2021, p.10). This aspect has a significant connection to intercultural awareness. As defined by Baker (2011), intercultural awareness in the context of English as a lingua franca refers to the recognition and understanding of how culturally influenced forms, practices, and frames of reference play a significant role in intercultural communication. Furthermore, it encompasses the capacity to effectively apply this understanding in practical situations. Intercultural Awareness Scale (ICAS), which was developed to evaluate students' intercultural awareness in the context of English language

instruction (Asma & Saka, 2020), is merely one among several researches that have been done to design intercultural awareness scales. Nevertheless, a deficiency exists in the field of intercultural awareness assessment as there is currently no established intercultural awareness scale that aligns with Baker's (2012) intercultural awareness model. Furthermore, this scale has not been utilized within the specific context of higher vocational English education in China. To address this gap, the present study has developed an intercultural awareness scale by drawing upon existing literature and the theoretical framework proposed by Baker (2011, 2012). This scale encompasses three distinct degrees of intercultural awareness, each characterized by specific components. The scale will also be employed to assess the degree of intercultural awareness among higher vocational English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners in the specific setting of Henan province, China.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Definition of ICA

The earliest definition of intercultural awareness has been supplied by researchers, with its origins extending back to the 1970s. Hanvey (1979) defines intercultural awareness as the capacity of individuals engaged in intercultural discourse to exhibit a heightened sensitivity towards cultural elements (Huang, 2022, p. 474)(Huang, 2022). Tomalin and Stempleski (2013) argue that persons who possess intercultural awareness demonstrate an increased level of sensitivity towards a wide range of cultural perspectives. Moreover, the notion of intercultural awareness can be comprehended as the formation of a connection between many distinct cultures, encompassing a form of interaction that integrates numerous cultural heritages (Byram & Zarate, 1997). Tomlinson and Masuhara (2004) argue that intercultural awareness involves a dynamic progression towards acquiring an internalized notion of cultural equality and an improved comprehension of both one's own culture and other cultures.

Baker (2011) offers a valuable portrayal that aims to enhance the precision of exploring intercultural awareness. According to the author, international awareness is a purposeful acknowledgment of the influence that culturally unique forms, practices, and attitudes exert on communication at the international level. Furthermore, it involves the capacity to effectively and adaptively employ this comprehension in immediate interpersonal exchanges. The study is based on the theoretical model of intercultural competence proposed by Chen & Starosta and the self-assessment scale of Chinese college students' intercultural communicative competence compiled by Wu Weiping. Combining with the actual situation of Chinese college students, the author compiled a scale of intercultural awareness among college students contains a set of evaluations including consciousness, emotion and behavior.

The results of the study found that although the overall situation of college students' intercultural awareness is good, there are certain differences in different dimensions of awareness. College students perform better in cultural confidence and self-control, flexibility and adaptability, tolerance and patience, while they need to improve communication skills, curiosity about different cultural knowledge and customs, and a sense of humor (Huang, 2022).

2.2 Levels of Intercultural Awareness

In Baker's (2011) study, a conceptual framework was put forth to elucidate the construct of intercultural awareness. This framework delineated three discrete levels, namely basic cultural awareness, advanced cultural awareness, and intercultural awareness. This paradigm covers two distinct forms of intercultural awareness: conceptual intercultural awareness and practice-oriented intercultural awareness. Both of these forms can be found at all levels within the model. The understanding of the higher level will exert influence on the lower level within this conceptual framework. The main focus of the introductory level is to develop an understanding of the cultural elements related to the target language. The practice-oriented approach to cultural awareness entails the comprehensive analysis and juxtaposition of many cultures on a broad and overarching scale. The second layer involves an elevated degree of complex conceptual intercultural understanding. This level of praxis involves the ability to surpass cultural biases and acknowledge the possibility of misinterpretations that can emerge due to varying cultural contexts. The final level is intricately linked to intercultural awareness, encompassing the understanding of effective cross-cultural communication. The research undertaken by Baker (2011) provides a comprehensive visual depiction of the model being examined as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Model of Intercultural Awareness (Baker, 2011, p. 203)

Numerous models have been devised to assist research across multiple levels or dimensions, owing to the extensive scope of intercultural awareness. The present study will employ Baker's (2011) intercultural awareness paradigm, comprising three distinct levels, namely basic cultural awareness, advanced cultural awareness, and intercultural awareness. This paradigm covers two distinct forms of intercultural awareness: conceptual intercultural awareness and practice-oriented intercultural awareness. Both of these kinds are seen at every level inside the model. In order to augment the precision of each level, Baker (2012) put forth a conceptual structure comprising discrete elements for the cultivation of intercultural awareness. The framework encompasses four components pertaining to fundamental cultural awareness, five components pertaining to enhanced cultural awareness, and three components pertaining to intercultural awareness.

The main objective of this research will be to construct the intercultural awareness scale based on the 12 components of ICA, as outlined by Baker (2012). Furthermore, this study will also include subthemes of basic cultural awareness and advanced cultural awareness as delineated by Abdzadeh and Baker (2020) into the framework of the intercultural awareness scale. The entire documentation of the instructional theoretical framework utilized in the development of the intercultural awareness scale can be found in Table 1.

Table 1: Instructional Theoretical Framework for the Intercultural Awareness Scale in this Research

Levels of ICA	Elements	Definition
Level 1: Basic Cultural Awareness	1) General definition of culture	1.1.1 Culture is a description of a particular way of life which expresses certain meanings and values not only in art and learning but also in institutions and ordinary behavior (Baldwin et al., 2006)(Chen & Starosta, n.d.).
	2) National definition of culture	1.1.2 National conceptions of cultural behavior based on personal experience from Chinese society.
	1.2 Influence of First Culture	Our own culturally induced behavior, values, and beliefs and the ability to articulate this (Baker, 2012).
	1.3.1 Self-stereotypes	The term stereotype is commonly used to refer to negative or positive judgments made about individuals based on any observable or believed group membership (Hoyt, 2012).
	1.3.2 Other stereotypes	1.3.1 The negative or positive judgments made about individuals based on Chinese culture.
		1.3.2 The negative or positive judgments made about individuals based on other cultures.
Level 2: Advanced Cultural Awareness	2.1 Relativity of cultural norms	Following Baker (2011), relativity of cultural norms refers to instances of the different interpretations cultural norms can have in different contexts.
	2.2 Awareness of different national cultural perspectives	There is a coexistence of different perspectives of national culture.
	2.3 Awareness of cultural identity	Collier & Thomas (1988) describe this as cultural identity, or the identification with and perceived acceptance into a

		group that has a shared system of symbols and meanings as well as norms for conduct.
	2.4 Awareness of cultural revision	Awareness that cultural understanding is open to change.
	2.5 Awareness of cultural differences	A detailed awareness of common ground and mismatch between specific cultures (Baker, 2012).
	2.6 Basic practice of intercultural communication	Practice to compare and mediate between cultures at a specific level (Baker, 2012).
Level 3: Intercultural Awareness	1.2 Culturally based frames	Culturally based frames of reference, forms, and communicative practices as being related both to specific cultures and also as emergent and hybrid in intercultural communication (Baker, 2012).
	3.2 Initial interaction in intercultural communication	Initial interaction in intercultural communication as possibly based on cultural stereotypes or generalizations but an ability to move beyond these through (Baker, 2012).
	3.3 Advanced intercultural communication	A capacity to negotiate and mediate between different emergent social culturally grounded communication modes and frames of reference based on the above understanding of culture in intercultural communication (Baker, 2012).

Note. Adapted from " From cultural awareness to intercultural awareness: Culture in ELT" by Baker, W., 2012, ELT journal, 66(1), 62-70.

2.3 Scales for Intercultural Awareness

A broad range of scholars have made significant advances in the advancement of scales utilized for the assessment of intercultural awareness. The researcher has conducted a comprehensive examination of the literature on scales for intercultural awareness. The following section provides an analysis of various scales that are frequently employed for assessing intercultural awareness.

The intercultural sensitivity scale, devised by Chen & Starosta (2000) , is widely regarded as the most influential scale for assessing intercultural awareness. The Intercultural Sensitivity Scale is composed of a comprehensive set of 24 items, which are classified into five distinctive factors: interaction attentiveness, impression rewarding, self-esteem, self-monitoring, and perspective taking. Thitima (2015) further enhanced the Cross-Cultural Sensitivity questionnaire by incorporating additional scales, namely the Cultural Integration Ability Scale (C Scale), Behavioral Ability Scale (B Scale), Knowledge Ability Scale (I Scale), Attitude towards Others Scale (A Scale), and Empathy Ability Scale (E Scale). These scales were introduced to facilitate the examination of intercultural awareness.

In addition, the suggested intercultural awareness assessments cover five distinct qualities, including interest, knowledge, perception, application, and skill, according to the most recent research on intercultural awareness scales (Xu, 2021).

Furthermore, Huang (2022) established a questionnaire with the objective of evaluating intercultural awareness. This instrument consists of 15 items that encompass six dimensions: flexibility and adaptability, tolerance and patience, sense of humor, curiosity about diverse

cultures' knowledge and customs, cultural confidence and self-control, and communication skills. The purpose of this survey was to assess the extent of intercultural awareness among college students (Huang, 2022, p. 475).

Based on the results of the literature analysis, several experts have made scales for intercultural awareness. Nevertheless, it is worth highlighting that none of the existing scales have incorporated the remarkable and insightful intercultural awareness framework of Will Baker. This signifies a gap in the current amount of research that necessitates further examination.

3. RESEARCH QUESTION AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Questions

- What are the components that influence the design of scale for intercultural awareness?
- What is the extent to which the suggested scale of intercultural awareness demonstrates validity and reliability?
- How is the structural model of the scale for the three levels of intercultural awareness?

3.2 Research Objectives

The objective of this study is to construct an intercultural awareness scale based on the guidelines provided by Baker (2012), which outline the levels and components of intercultural awareness. Additionally, the existing literature pertaining to scales measuring intercultural awareness will serve as a valuable resource for informing the specific formulation of questions within the intercultural awareness scale employed in this research. Furthermore, the present study aims to assess the proposed intercultural awareness scale's validity and reliability through the utilization of the developed scale to the students in one higher vocational college in Henan province.

3.3 Research Design

To develop a questionnaire for assessing the intercultural awareness of higher vocational students, the existing questionnaires on intercultural awareness from previous studies were utilized. These questionnaires were selected based on a review of relevant literature, including the intercultural awareness scale developed by Asma and Saka (2020), the intercultural awareness scale developed by Huang (2022) and the intercultural sensitivity scale devised by Chen & Starosta (2000). Additionally, the suggested scale for intercultural awareness has been subjected to analysis by two specialists in the fields of intercultural awareness and scale design in order to ensure its validity.

The population size of this educational institution amounts to 6000 students, encompassing both first-year and second-year undergraduates. Given that the research focuses on the internship experiences of college students, it has specifically omitted graduating students who will be leaving the institution for their internships in their third year. The sample size is determined using a 90% confidence level, a 5% margin of error, a 50% population proportion, and a population size of 16000. Upon inputting the aforementioned data into an online sample

size calculator, the resulting suggested sample size is determined to be 260. This study encompasses a total of 274 participants, consisting of 64 male and 207 female students enrolled in a higher vocational college in China.

The researchers employed a hierarchical clustering sampling strategy to identify the students who participated in this study. The process of hierarchical clustering entails the creation of a binary merge tree in Table 2, which commences with the representation of individual data components as leaves, each handled as a distinct set consisting of a single member. The procedure proceeds by iteratively merging the two subsets that are deemed to be the most similar, as determined by a specific criterion, and this process continues until the root of the tree is reached, thereby covering all the components under examination (Nielsen, 2016).

Table 2: Binary Merge Tree for Hierarchical Clustering

4. DEVELOPING THE SCALE FOR ICA

4.1 Proposed Design of Scale for ICA

The researchers commenced the process of scale development by conducting a comprehensive literature review in the relevant field. A question pool was generated, comprising a collection of probable items. The items have been uniquely constructed based on three distinct degrees of intercultural awareness: basic cultural awareness, advanced cultural awareness, and intercultural awareness. The draft form comprised a total of 50 items. The materials that had been prepared were requested for assessment by specialists in the subject. In order to achieve this objective, the form was distributed to two specialists in the field of measurement and evaluation, as well as two specialists in the relevant domain, as previously utilized by Tavşancıl (2014). Based on the feedback received, an agreement was reached among the majority of experts to remove four elements, which were subsequently excluded from the scale. The final iteration of the scale was developed as a 5-point Likert scale consisting of 46 items. The administered scale was administered to the group of participants involved in the research study. The participants assigned scores to the statements on a scale ranging from 5 (indicating complete agreement) to 1 (indicating complete disagreement). Based on the expert group's

validating suggestions, the questionnaire has been divided into four distinct parts. The first part encompasses questions Q1 to Q6 and focuses on gathering personal information. The second part, consisting of questions Q7 to Q16, aims to assess basic cultural awareness. The third part, comprising questions Q17 to Q32, delves into advanced cultural awareness. Lastly, the fourth part, encompassing questions Q33 to Q46, explores intercultural awareness.

4.2 Validity and Reliability of ICA Scale

The collected data were analyzed through Quantitative Data Analysis Software (SPSS). Data of two participants using less than 40 seconds to finish the questionnaire have been deleted to guarantee the validity. The exploratory factor analysis was performed to determine to construct validity of the scale. To obtain information about the item discrimination values, total item correlation was checked. The internal consistency reliability was explored through Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient.

4.2.1 Reliability

The internal consistency reliability was explored through Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient (Saka & Asma, 2020, p. 450). Cronbach (1951) developed the coefficient alpha applicable to most item-scoring systems which has become the most widely used reliability index. The reliability of the ICA scale in this research has also been analyzed with Cronbach's Alpha in SPSS 26. Based on the SPSS analyzing results, the Alpha values from .70 to .95 are considered as acceptable (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011). Cronbach's alpha coefficients of 0.9 or above indicate very good reliability for the test or scale, between 0.8 and 0.9 indicates good reliability, between 0.7 and 0.8 indicates acceptable reliability, between 0.6 and 0.7 indicates fair reliability, between 0.5 and 0.6 indicates less than optimal reliability, and if it is below 0.5, the questionnaire has to be considered for reformatting. As the reliability analyzing results in Table 3 indicate, the value of Cronbach's Alpha for all the items equals 0.969. The values of Cronbach's Alpha for the three levels of intercultural awareness are 0.936, 0.941, and 0.950 individually. Therefore, the ICA scale in this research is with very good reliability from different dimensions.

Table 3: Reliability Analysis from Different Dimensions

Reliability Statistics	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
All the items	0.969	46
L1 of ICA	0.936	10
L2 of ICA	0.941	16
L3 of ICA	0.950	14

Note: Q1-6 are students' basic information; Q7-16 indicate the first level of ICA (Basic cultural awareness); Q17-32 indicate the second level of ICA (Advanced cultural awareness); Q33-46 indicate the third level of ICA (Intercultural awareness).

4.2.2 Validity

The validity evidence of the Intercultural Awareness Scale in this research was provided by the exploratory factor analysis and the correlation values for every item.

The principal component analysis method has been utilized for the factor analysis. Before computing the exploratory factor analysis, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test and Bartlett Sphericity test results were taken into account to test sampling adequacy which has also been used in the research of Saka & Asma (2020).

As is shown in the Table 4, the total items' value of Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy equals 0.950. The KMO values for the three levels of ICA are 0.923, 0.926 and 0.928 representatively. Since the KMO value is higher than .90 are considerably marvelous for factor analysis (Tavşancıl, 2014), this research on the higher vocational students' intercultural awareness is suitable for factor analysis on all the items and all the three levels of ICA.

For Bartlett's test, if the significance is less than 0.05, the original hypothesis is rejected, indicating that the factor analysis can be done. If the original hypothesis is not rejected, indicating that these variables may provide some information independently, and it is not suitable for factor analysis. As shown in Table 4, the p value of the Bartlett's test for all the items equals .000 (<.05) indicating that the original hypothesis is rejected and the factor analysis can be done in the ICA scale in this research. As for the three levels of ICA, all of them have 0.00 p values indicating that variables for the three levels of ICA are correlated with each other individually, factor analysis is effective, and the degree is appropriate.

Table 4: KMO and Bartlett's Test of the ICA Scale

	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy	Bartlett's Test of Sphericity		
		Approx. Chi-Square	df	Sig.
All Items	.950	12402.549	780	0.00
L1 of ICA	.923	2285.110	45	0.00
L2 of ICA	.926	4498.338	120	0.00
L3 of ICA	.928	3463.306	91	0.00

Note: Q1-6 are students' basic information; Q7-16 indicate the first level of ICA (Basic cultural awareness); Q17-32 indicate the second level of ICA (Advanced cultural awareness); Q33-46 indicate the third level of ICA (Intercultural awareness).

4.3 Factor Analysis of the ICA Scale

As for finalizing the number of factors, Cattell (1966) emphasized the point where the variance's downward fall and the straight line representing the scree meet is typically considered the cutoff point for determining the number of factors. In the scree plot in Figure 2 generated from the factor analysis of SPSS 26, there is the downward fall from component 1 to component 3 and then the line from component 4 to component 40 generally remains straight. Therefore, the intercultural awareness scale of this research includes three components or factors based on the data analyzing results.

Figure 2: Scree plot

4.3.1 Factor Analysis Results

As for the variables for every factor, this research has designed the model that Factor 1 (First level of ICA) includes Q7 to Q16, Factor 2 (Second level of ICA) includes Q17 to Q32, Factor 3 (Third level of ICA) includes Q33 to Q46. Factor analysis results of the collected data have been illustrated in Table X below to evaluate the designed model for the intercultural awareness scale. The Factor Analysis results in Table 5 reveal that Factor 1 measures Q8, Q9, Q10, Q11, Q12, Q13, Q14, Q15, and Q16 at 0.000*** respectively. At a significance level of 0.000***, the original hypothesis is rejected. Additionally, the standardized loading coefficients for all these variables exceed 0.6, indicating a substantial amount of variance explained. This suggests that the variables can be effectively represented on the same factor. As shown in Table 5, the measurement items of Factor 2, namely Q18, Q19, Q20, Q21, Q23, Q25, Q28, Q29, Q30, Q31, and Q32, all exhibit a level of significance of 0.000***. Consequently, the original hypothesis is rejected. Additionally, the standardized loading coefficient for these items exceeds 0.6, indicating that they provide sufficient variance explained. This suggests that these variables can be considered to belong to the same factor.

Moreover, as shown in Table 5, the measurement items of Factor 3, namely Q34, Q35, Q37, Q38, Q39, Q40, Q41, Q42, Q43, Q44, Q45, and Q46, have a level of significance of 0.000***. As a result, the original hypothesis is rejected. Additionally, the standardized loading coefficients of these items are greater than 0.6, indicating that they have sufficient variance explained. This suggests that these variables can be considered to belong to the same factor.

Table 5: Factor Analysis Results of the Designed Factor Components Model

factor	variable	Non-standard load factor	standard load factor	z	S.E.	P
Factor 1	Q7	1	0.731	-	-	-
	Q8	1.048	0.827	14.041	0.075	0.000***
	Q9	1.06	0.87	14.849	0.071	0.000***
	Q10	1.105	0.884	15.114	0.073	0.000***
	Q11	1.06	0.795	13.462	0.079	0.000***
	Q12	1.061	0.803	13.594	0.078	0.000***
	Q13	1.088	0.869	14.82	0.073	0.000***
	Q14	1.114	0.899	15.383	0.072	0.000***
	Q14	0.635	0.439	7.224	0.088	0.000***
Factor 2	Q15	0.854	0.661	11.043	0.077	0.000***
	Q16	0.905	0.7	11.727	0.077	0.000***
	Q17	1	0.81	-	-	-
	Q18	1.071	0.869	17.681	0.061	0.000***
	Q19	1.069	0.858	17.345	0.062	0.000***
	Q20	1.119	0.87	17.712	0.063	0.000***
	Q21	0.31	0.179	2.949	0.105	0.003***
	Q22	1.087	0.885	18.196	0.06	0.000***
	Q23	0.817	0.564	9.991	0.082	0.000***
	Q24	1.096	0.876	17.926	0.061	0.000***
	Q25	1.088	0.86	17.406	0.063	0.000***
	Q26	0.839	0.647	11.795	0.071	0.000***
	Q27	0.609	0.433	7.404	0.082	0.000***
	Q28	1.128	0.86	17.407	0.065	0.000***
Factor 3	Q29	1.077	0.86	17.425	0.062	0.000***
	Q30	0.511	0.305	5.09	0.1	0.000***
	Q31	1.011	0.775	14.955	0.068	0.000***
	Q32	1.02	0.825	16.372	0.062	0.000***
	Q33	1	0.741	-	-	-
	Q34	1.056	0.761	13.032	0.081	0.000***
	Q35	0.843	0.486	8.068	0.105	0.000***
	Q36	1.066	0.813	14.03	0.076	0.000***
	Q37	1.172	0.862	14.985	0.078	0.000***
	Q38	1.092	0.745	12.721	0.086	0.000***
	Q39	0.959	0.612	10.282	0.093	0.000***
Factor 3	Q40	1.151	0.816	14.076	0.082	0.000***
	Q41	1.128	0.796	13.696	0.082	0.000***
	Q42	1.189	0.885	15.445	0.077	0.000***
	Q42	0.927	0.642	10.828	0.086	0.000***
	Q43	1.16	0.861	14.976	0.077	0.000***
	Q44	1.15	0.882	15.389	0.075	0.000***

Note: ***, **, * represents the level of significance of 1%, 5% and 10% respectively

4.3.2 AVE and CR for Every Factor

The findings from the assessments conducted on the average variance extracted (AVE) and combined reliability (CR) for every factor in Table 6 below indicate that: Based on the first factor, the average variance extracted (AVE) has a value of 0.606, above the threshold of 0.5. Additionally, the combined reliability (CR) has a value of 0.938, surpassing the threshold of 0.7. These findings suggest that the extraction of the measures inside the factor is of high quality. According to Factor 2, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) has a value of 0.512, surpassing the threshold of 0.5. Additionally, the Combined Reliability (CR) has a value of 0.94, beyond the threshold of 0.7. These results indicate that the extraction of the measures inside the factor is of high quality. According to Factor 3, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) has a value of 0.572, surpassing the threshold of 0.5. Additionally, the Combined Reliability (CR) has a value of 0.949, beyond the recommended threshold of 0.7. These results indicate that the extraction of the measures inside the factor is of high quality.

Table 6: Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and Combined Reliability (CR) of Each Factor for the ICA Scale

Factor	AVE	CR
Factor 1	0.606	0.938
Factor 2	0.512	0.94
Factor 3	0.572	0.949

4.4 Evaluation of the Model for ICA Scale

4.4.1 Analysis of the Proposed Coefficients of the Three Factors

According to the model path coefficient for the three factors listed in Table 7 below, it is evident that the significance P value for the relationship between Factor 1 and Factor 2 is 0.000***. The significance, represented horizontally, indicates that the original assumption is rejected, thus confirming the validity of this path. Furthermore, the influence factor for this path is determined to be 0.896. Based on the observed correlation between Factor 2 and Factor 3, the statistical significance, as indicated by the p-value of 0.000***, suggests that the initial assumption is rejected. Consequently, this pathway can be considered valid, with a substantial effect factor of 0.976. Based on the correlation between Factor 1 and Factor 3, the obtained significance p-value is 0.188. Furthermore, there is no statistically significant relationship observed in the horizontal direction. Consequently, the initial assumption cannot be refuted, indicating that this pathway lacks validity.

Table 7: Regression Coefficients of the Three Levels of Intercultural Awareness

Latent variable	→	Explicit variable	Non standardized coefficient	Standardization coefficient	Standard error	Z	P
Level 1	→	Level 2	0.907	0.896	0.072	12.646	0.000***
Level 2	→	Level 3	0.899	0.976	0.103	8.725	0.000***
Level 1	→	Level 3	-0.11	-0.118	0.084	-1.316	0.188

Note: ***, **, * represents the level of significance of 1%, 5% and 10% respectively

4.4.2 Structural Equation Model (SEM) Analysis Results

The Amos 17.0 software was used to fulfill the structural equation model (SEM) analysis of the proposed ICA scale in order to assess the adequacy of the scale. The model fit indices were derived by validating the hypothesis model using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). As shown in Table 8, the RMR, CFI, NNFI, TLI, IFI, PGFI, PNFI, PCFI, SRMR values of indicators of structural fit models for the proposed ICA scale are satisfactory with the revised structural model by eliminating the variable with low regression value. The goodness-of-fit indices of the structural equation model (SEM) indicate that the ICA scale's structural model path diagram, as depicted in Figure X, exhibits a strong fit with the observed data. These indices fall within the acceptable range and align with the evaluation criteria for overall model fit in SEM. Consequently, we can infer that the improved ICA scale model demonstrates high validity.

Table 8: Values of Indicators of Structural Fit Models for ICA Scale

Indicators	RMR	CFI	NNFI	TLI	IFI	PGFI	PNFI	PCFI	SRMR
Criteria	<0.05	>0.9	>0.9	>0.9	>0.9	>0.5	>0.5	>0.5	<0.1
Value	0.040	0.916	0.901	0.901	0.917	0.605	0.753	0.773	0.055

Figure 3: Revised ICA Scale Structure Model Path

Note. ICA L1 = Basic cultural awareness (DC = Definition of culture, IFC = Influence of first culture, STER = Stereotype), ICA L2 = Advanced cultural awareness (RCN = Relativity of cultural norms, ANCP = Awareness of different national cultural perspectives, ACI = Awareness of cultural identity, ACR = Awareness of cultural revision, ACD = Awareness of cultural differences, BPIC = Basic practice of intercultural communication), ICA L3 = Intercultural awareness (CBF = Culturally based frames, IIIC = Initial interaction in intercultural communication, AIC = Advanced intercultural communication)

As shown in Figure 3, the structural model for ICA scale has been revised based on the structural equation model analysis results in order to guarantee the requirements of the Indicators of Structural Fit Models in Table X above. Therefore, the revised ICA scale includes ICA L1 (Basic cultural awareness) which is analyzed from three perspectives: DC (Definition of culture) with Q8, IFC (Influence of first culture) with Q9, Q10 and Q11, STER (Stereotype) with Q13 and Q14. Moreover, the ICA L2 (Advanced cultural awareness) is analyzed from six perspectives: RCN (Relativity of cultural norms) with Q18, ANCP (Awareness of different national cultural perspectives) with Q19 and Q20, ACI (Awareness of cultural identity) with Q21, ACR (Awareness of cultural revision) with Q23, ACD (Awareness of cultural differences) with Q25, BPIC (Basic practice of intercultural communication) with Q29, Q30 and Q31. As for the third level of ICA L3 (Intercultural awareness), three dimensions have been analyzed in this scale. The first dimension is CBF (Culturally based frames) with Q34 and Q35. The second dimension is IIIC (Initial interaction in intercultural communication) with Q37 and Q38. The third dimension is AIC (Advanced intercultural communication) with Q44, Q45 and Q46.

5. DISCUSSION

The intercultural awareness scale has been constructed based on the 12 components of ICA (Baker, 2012). Furthermore, the developed ICA scale also incorporates subthemes of basic cultural awareness and advanced cultural awareness as delineated by Abdzadeh and Baker (2020). Moreover, the developed intercultural awareness scale has also combined the ICA scale of Asma and Saka (2020), Huang (2022) and the intercultural sensitivity scale devised by Chen & Starosta (2000). All these components are the influencing factors for the developing of the intercultural awareness scale in this research.

As the reliability analyzing results of the developed ICA scale indicate, the value of Cronbach's Alpha for all the items equals 0.969. The values of Cronbach's Alpha for the three levels of intercultural awareness are 0.936, 0.941, and 0.950 individually. Therefore, the ICA scale in this research is with very good reliability from different dimensions with Cronbach's alpha coefficients of above 0.9 (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011).

As for the validity of the developed ICA scale, the total items' value of Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy equals 0.950. The KMO values for the three levels of ICA are 0.923, 0.926 and 0.928 representatively. Since the KMO value is higher than .90 are considerably marvelous for factor analysis (Tavşancıl, 2014), the developed ICA scale is also valid for further factor analysis. As for the variables for every factor, this research has designed the model that Factor 1 (First level of ICA) includes Q7 to Q16, Factor 2 (Second level of ICA)

includes Q17 to Q32, Factor 3 (Third level of ICA) includes Q33 to Q46. Based on the factor analysis result, Q7, Q17 and Q33 with null p value have been deleted from the developed ICA scale.

Based on the structural equation model (SEM) analysis results, the structural model for ICA scale has been revised accordingly. Therefore, the revised ICA scale includes ICA L1 (Basic cultural awareness) with Q8, Q9, Q10, Q11, Q13 and Q14. Moreover, the ICA L2 (Advanced cultural awareness) is analyzed with Q18, Q19, Q20, Q21, Q23, Q25, Q29, Q30 and Q31. In addition, the third level of ICA L3 (Intercultural awareness) is analyzed with Q34 Q35, Q37, Q38, Q44, Q45 and Q46.

6. CONCLUSION

The three levels of the intercultural awareness scale developed in this research has been constructed based on the 12 components of ICA in the intercultural awareness theory of Baker (2012). Moreover, the reliability and validity of the developed intercultural awareness scale are satisfactory. Based on the factor analysis and the structural equation model analysis results, the developed ICA scale has been revised accordingly. The goodness-of-fit indices of the revised ICA scale exhibits a strong fit with the observed data.

This research has filled the gap that there is no intercultural awareness scale developed on the basis of the intercultural awareness theory of Baker (2011, 2012). In higher vocational English education, this intercultural awareness scale can also be used to figure out the extend of students' three levels of intercultural awareness in order to promote the efficiency of higher vocational English education in China.

Nevertheless, the scope of this study is restricted to a specific higher vocational institution located in Henan province. It is recommended that the scale measuring the three levels of intercultural awareness be administered to students residing in different areas of China.

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